

Mural Quick Start Guide

Suggestions and tips for using Mural during CSCCE trainings and community calls

Created by staff at the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE)

Table of Contents

About the guide	2
Acknowledgements	2
Citing and reusing this guide	2
1. Mural access	3
2. Using Mural to collaboratively create, brainstorm, and problem-solve	3
3. Saving your work to submit as homework	5

About the guide

[Mural](#) is a web-based whiteboarding application, which CSCCE uses in various trainings and occasionally at our monthly community calls. This guide contains some quick tips to help you to configure and use Mural. They are organized into three key areas that describe:

1. Mural access
2. Using Mural to collaboratively create, brainstorm, and problem-solve
3. Saving your work to submit as homework

If you need help with something not covered in this guide, please visit the [Mural Help Center](#).

Any questions? Email: tech.help@cscce.org

Acknowledgements

CSCCE uses the CRediT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

KATIE PRATT - Conceptualization, Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing, Visualization

ALICE MARTINIC - Writing - Original draft preparation

LOU WOODLEY - Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Reviewing and Editing

Citing and reusing this guide

CITATION AND REUSE

“Mural Quick Start Guide: Suggestions and tips for using Mural during CSCCE trainings and community calls,” by Katie Pratt, Alice Martinic, and Lou Woodley is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International ([CC BY 4.0](#)) license.

Cite as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2025) Mural Quick Start Guide: Suggestions and tips for using Mural during CSCCE trainings and community calls. Pratt, Martinic, and Woodley doi: [10.5281/zenodo.16739286](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16739286)

Contact the CSCCE for other permissions by emailing info@cscce.org. The CSCCE logo is a trademark of CSCCE.

Please clearly attribute any modified use of this material as “Adapted from an original by the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) under a CC BY 4.0 license, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.16739286](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16739286). We request that the CSCCE logo is clearly visible next to the attribution, that you indicate which is the original text, and include the full citation as described above.

Last updated August 2025

1. Mural access

You do not need to create an account to access Mural, however if you find the platform useful and would like to use it more in your own work, you can [create a free account](#) or choose one of their paid options for access to more features.

You can use Mural on a variety of devices. [More information about browser requirements](#).

During CSCCE trainings, we use password-protected Mural boards. You can find the link to your Mural board in Canvas and/or the shared notes doc for a session, next to which will be the password you need to log in (passwords are case sensitive).

If you have any trouble finding the login details for a Mural, please contact training@cscce.org and a member of our training team will get back to you.

2. Using Mural to collaboratively create, brainstorm, and problem-solve

Below are some tips for navigating and adding content to Mural. Please reach out to your instructors if you need additional support.

- **Basic navigation**
 - Click “Navigation settings” on the bottom right-hand corner of the toolbar to choose either trackpad mode or mouse mode.
 - Click the map icon to discover the overall contents of the board – and which bit you are currently focused on.
 - Here you can also find controls to support zooming in and out.
 - You can also expand (see a pop up) of different elements by holding the “X” button and hovering over them from far away.
- **Adding elements:** On the left side of your screen, you will find the following tools to add various elements, such as:
 - **Templates:** This menu includes access to generic Mural templates, as well as any template boards you have created.

2. USING MURAL TO COLLABORATIVELY CREATE, BRAINSTORM, AND PROBLEM-SOLVE

- **Sticky notes:** Choose your preferred shape and color, and then add a sticky note to your Mural. Double click a sticky note to add or edit text. In CSCCE activities, you will often be asked to add your thoughts to sticky notes.
- **Text:** Add text boxes to your Mural. You can choose “headings,” “paragraphs,” or “comments.” We generally use this function for labels and instructions. It is less likely that we will ask you to use this feature.
- **Shapes and connectors:** Add shapes and use connectors to create diagrams and illustrate ideas.
- **Icons:** Search for an icon, and then drag it from the menu and onto your Mural.
- **Images:** You can search the web for images and gifs, or you can upload logos and other graphics to include in your Mural.
- **Mind maps:** Click this menu item to start making a mind map in your Mural. You can create branches by clicking on the icons surrounding the parent node. [Only available when logged into Mural]
- **Tables and areas:** Create tables or divide your Mural into defined areas.
- **Draw:** Sketch with virtual pens, markers, and highlighters.
- **Content library:** You can customize this part of the menu by right clicking an element you’ve created and then adding it to the content library. [Only available when logged into Mural]
- **Import files:** upload documents from your computer or connect to Google Drive and other services, e.g., if you want to import a screenshot to work on collaboratively.

Typically, in a CSCCE training, we’ll scaffold a board with elements in place for you to work with, but in some courses, we also give you the opportunity to build more creatively, if you like.

- **To edit elements:**
 - Double-click sticky notes, text boxes and tiles on the board to edit their text.
 - Click any element to access a toolbar to change its attributes, including color and size.
 - Right click any element to find more options such as locking and duplicating elements – locking can be useful to ensure that others don't accidentally move your content when making their own!

3. Saving your work to submit as homework

In some of CSCCE's trainings, you will be asked to submit something you created in Mural as a PDF as part of your homework assignments. You can save entire Mural boards, or small sections of boards, by following these steps:

- Click the dropdown arrow to the right of the Mural's title

- Select **download Mural**
- Click on the **format** dropdown and choose "PDF"
- Select which parts of the mural you want to export:
 - **All content** - exports the entire mural
 - **Selection** - lets you adjust a selection area to pick specific content
- Click **Download**

That's it – you're good to go!